

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF PROTECTING WOMEN FROM VIOLENCE AND VIOLENCE IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12770525>

Abstract: this article reveals the socio-philosophical aspects of creating an environment of intolerance to oppression and violence in society by clarifying the socio-philosophical, pedagogical-psychological and sociological factors of protecting women from oppression and violence, increasing the socio-political activity of women in the fight against family violence , the educational and preventive tasks aimed at strengthening their place and position in the family and society, developing their intellectual and creative abilities and forming their legal culture were analyzed.

Key words: gender equality, oppression, violence, social outlook, social mechanism, law, legal culture, socio-political activity, social protection, social stereotypes, family values.

Illegal acts that encroach on women's life, health, sexual integrity, honor, dignity and other rights and freedoms protected by law by exerting physical, mental, sexual or economic influence on women in the world or by threatening to use such influence measures tasks aimed at prevention are becoming more urgent. At the same time, there is an increasing need to protect women from oppression and violence, increase their social activity, ensure their employment, develop their legal culture, and reevaluate gender stereotypes in social relations. For this, it is considered a priority to study the socio-philosophical aspects of creating an environment of intolerance to oppression and violence in society based on the development and implementation of gender policy, state programs and strategies in the field of protection of women from oppression and violence.

To take measures to eliminate the causes and conditions that lead to oppression and violence against women in the world's advanced scientific research institutes and international centers, to create effective organizational and legal mechanisms to prevent, identify and put an end to oppression and violence in various forms many research works are being conducted and various social projects are being implemented. Based on such studies, a person who has committed a violent situation once has a high probability of repeating this situation again, it is very necessary to be aware of and prevent all forms of enabling violence, women who suffer from domestic violence, even women who

refuse help for some reasons, need the social support of society. it is concluded that it is necessary to create a social mechanism that works effectively in this situation. Therefore, it is important to improve the system of protection of women from oppression and violence and to form a social worldview based on the expansion of social research on this issue.

In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the tasks of "continuing the policy of ensuring gender equality, increasing the social and political activity of women, and implementing reforms to support them"[1] have been separately defined. Based on this, a number of scientific researches are being conducted to improve the system of protection of women from oppression and violence, to develop a new social mechanism aimed at supporting their social initiative.

PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated February 18, 2020 "Healthy social and spiritual environment in society, further support of the neighborhood institution and family and women Decree No. PF-5938 "On measures to bring the system of work with women to a new level" dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution" No. PF-5325 , Decision No. PQ-4235 of March 7, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship", 562 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" Laws of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2018 "Approval of the Regulation on the procedure for providing affordable housing to women in difficult social situations, disabled, low-income mothers, raising their children in single-parent families and in need of improving housing conditions" serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks specified in the Decision VM-285 and other regulatory legal documents on the subject.

Social-philosophical, sociological aspects of protection of women from oppression and violence of various forms in Uzbekistan, raising their activity and status in society S.T. Nurmatova, E. Sultonova, G. Matkarimova, Sh. Sodikova, N. Latipova, G. Tagieva, N. Nishonova, M. Gafforova, G. Ganieva, N.M. Muraveva, Kh. Nasrullaeva, N. Joraeva, S. It was studied in the studies of scientists such as Safaeva, N. Annaeva, G. Akhmedova [2].

Through this, it is aimed to protect the rights of women, ensure their interests, realize their abilities, talents and opportunities, and make them equal,

active and productive members of society. For this, there is a need for a socio-philosophical analysis of the mechanisms for eliminating the causes and conditions that lead to oppression and violence against women.

The following tasks are important in improving the system of protection against harassment and violence against women and shaping the social outlook:

to study the essence and types of oppression and violence, to study the legal basis of prevention of violence in the family.

scientifically justifying that raising legal culture among women is a necessary condition for preventing harassment and violence.

Research that increasing women's socio-political activity is an important factor in ensuring gender equality in the country

to reconsider the influence of social stereotypes in the social protection of women and to shed light on the role of strengthening family values.

In conclusion, it can be said that determining the level of immanence characteristics of each type of activity in the social protection of women is important in increasing the effectiveness of this system. First of all, this is closely related to the active participation of women in the development of the country, the increase of their important role in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in the country and the family, and the expansion of opportunities for cooperative decision-making.

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